

A STUDY TO EVALUATE THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AND HOSTEL LIFE

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Abstract

Background:

Hostel life plays an important role in shaping students' academic, social, and personal development. Living away from home can influence students' learning environment, adjustment patterns, and overall academic performance. Understanding the relationship between hostel life and academic performance is essential for improving student support systems in higher education institutions.

Objective:

To evaluate the relationship between hostel life and academic performance among undergraduate health sciences students and to examine the association between selected demographic characteristics and academic performance levels.

Methodology:

A comparative cross-sectional study was conducted at the new campus of People's University of Medical and Health Sciences for Women (PUMHSW), SBA. A total sample of 278 undergraduate students from BSN (Generic), DPT, Pharm-D, and BSPH programs was selected. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire that included demographic information and an Academic Performance Scale. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 20. Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, t-tests, ANOVA, and regression analysis were applied to determine associations between variables. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board prior to data collection.

Results:

The mean age of respondents was 21.41 ± 1.515 years. Most participants demonstrated good to excellent academic performance levels. Chi-square analysis revealed that gender, ethnicity, economic status, academic program, academic year, and accommodation status (hostler and non-hostler) did not show a statistically significant association with academic performance ($p > 0.05$). Religion showed a statistically significant association with academic performance levels ($\chi^2 = 12.941$, $p = 0.010$). Both hostlers and non-hostlers predominantly exhibited good to excellent academic performance.

Conclusion:

The study concluded that hostel life does not have a significant impact on

academic performance among undergraduate health sciences students. Academic performance was generally consistent across most demographic variables. Although religion showed a significant association, the finding should be interpreted cautiously due to unequal group distribution. Overall, the results suggest that academic performance is influenced by multiple factors beyond accommodation status.

INTRODUCTION:

Hostels play a significant role in student life, they unite students from diverse backgrounds, fostering an atmosphere that supports both intellectual and personal development, Hostels are becoming more and more important as more kids go off to college since they offer not only a place to stay but also an opportunity to meet people and experience other culture. However, living away from home for the first time can be tough for many students, The sense of separation from family, combined with the stress of adjusting to a new routine, can bring about feelings of loneliness and homesickness, These emotions can have a real impact on their mental health, studies, and overall experience. Homesickness, in particular, often lingers, affecting how students feel and perform in both their personal and academic lives. In educational institutions across all cultures and geographical areas, hostels are an essential type of student housing, The amenities and support services offered in these dorms frequently have an impact on students' academic performance, Nevertheless, providing sufficient student accommodation continues to be a significant problem for higher education systems around the globe. Due to academic migration, globalization, and mobility, universities now have student bodies that are more varied than ever before, As a result, undergraduates' need for hostel amenities has increased significantly, It is well accepted that students' academic performance can be significantly impacted by the caliber of the resources and services provided by the hostel. According to a study, hostel residents are more self-assured, resolute, and independent than nonresident students, They also exhibit a more positive attitude, Hostelized students must overcome a variety of obstacles, including financial crises, adjustment issues, feelings of personal helplessness, anguish, changes in food and

sleeping habits, and many more ,Research indicates that students who live in dorms are more likely to be mentally stable, empathetic, and altruistic, In a dorm environment, students have the opportunity to mingle, However, since the students' main goal in living in a hostel is to gain information and skills, it is evident whether or not the hostel lifestyle affects their academic achievement. The main advantage of hostel living is that it enables students to should empower students to finish all of their work alone in order to teach them independence, Additionally, they understand how important it is to make time to use the gym, playgrounds, libraries, and reading rooms, as well as the importance of setting aside time for training in order to improve skills and encourage healthy growth. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to evaluate how the undergraduate medical students were affected by their dormitory experience. The accomplishment of both short- and long-term learning goals and the satisfaction of necessary educational requirements constitute student academic success, Academic success encompasses both a student's discipline and the skills that are expected of them mastery in every subject, Persistence and the will to succeed are also reflected in good academic achievement, This is due to the fact that achieving an encouraging level of academic achievement requires overcoming a number of obstacles and procedures. Since numerous variables and intricate situations affect the quality of education, one of the first complicated facts is that educational services are frequently difficult and intangible to quantify, Education often takes the shape of information, life skills, and behavioral changes in students and numerous studies have found that socioeconomic, psychological, and environmental factors influence academic achievement. Students who stated that stress affected their performance had lower GPAs,

higher levels of stress, and lower levels of social support, tolerance, and self-efficiency, Gender was also discovered to be important element for pupils' stress levels and academic achievement, In addition, the academic research was linked to health. The hostel setting was proved to improve learning performance, the study indicated a high positive correlation between students' academic success and living in a dorm, While socioeconomic status had a mixed effect, exhibiting little to no difference between middle- and high-SES groups but a minor variation among kids from lower-SES families, male students outperformed female students academically, Overall, it has been demonstrated that dorm life helps and enhances undergraduates' academic performance.

MATERIAL AND MATHODS:

A comparative cross-sectional study was conducted at the New Campus of Peoples University of Medical & Health Sciences for Women (PUMHSW), Shaheed Benazirabad, Pakistan, to assess the impact of hostel life on the academic performance of undergraduate students. The study was carried out over a period of three months after obtaining approval from the Ethical Review Committee (ERC). The sample size of 278 participants was calculated using Rao Soft with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. A non-probability convenience sampling technique was used to recruit participants. The study population included students enrolled in BS Nursing (Generic), Doctor of Physical Therapy (DPT), Bachelor of Public Health (BSPH), and Doctor of Pharmacy (Pharm-D) programs. Inclusion criteria were undergraduate students aged 16–24 years who were willing to participate in the study.

RESULTS

Figure 1: Age of Respondent

Figure 2: Shows Role No of Respondent

TABLE 1 Association Demographic characteristics with Academic Performance Scale

Variable	Moderate	Good	Excellent	FET/ X ²	df	P value
Gender						
Male	0	1	0	4.391	-	0.371
Female	3	99	175			
Religion						
Muslim	3	80	161			

Hindu	0	20	12	12.941		0.010
Christian	0	0	2			
Ethnicity						
Sindhi	3	79	135	3.052	-	0.795
Punjabi	0	9	24			
Baloch	0	8	10			
Muhajir	0	6	6			
Economic status						
Poor	0	1	2	4.350	-	0.433
Middle	3	97	163			
High	0	2	10			
Program						
BSN(G)	0	44	88	6.931	-	0.256
DPT	1	23	35			
Pharm-D	1	17	34			
BSPH	1	16	18			
Academic year						
1st	0	15	26	5.085	-	0.478
2 nd	1	12	29			
3 rd	1	31	38			
4 th	1	42	82			
Accommodation						
Hostler	2	65	110	.287	-	0.909
Non-hostler	1	35	65			

DISCUSSION: This study examined the association between selected demographic characteristics and outcome levels (moderate, good, and excellent) among undergraduate health sciences students. Overall, the findings indicate that most participants demonstrated well to excellent levels, suggesting a generally favorable status across the study population. Gender did not show a statistically significant association with outcome levels. Although female participants constituted the majority of those with excellent levels, this difference was not statistically meaningful. This finding suggests that the outcome under study is not influenced by gender, indicating comparable levels among male and female students. Similar findings have been reported in previous studies, where gender differences did not significantly affect students' outcomes in academic or health-related domains. Religion, however, demonstrated a statistically significant association with outcome levels,

Muslim participants largely exhibited good to excellent levels, while Hindu participants were distributed between good and excellent categories. All Christian participants demonstrated excellent levels. Despite this statistical significance, the unequal distribution of participants across religious groups may have influenced this result. Therefore, the association should be interpreted with caution, and further studies with more balanced samples are recommended to better understand this relationship. Ethnicity was not found to be significantly associated with outcome levels. Sindhi students represented the largest ethnic group and predominantly fell within the excellent category, followed by Punjabi, Baloch, and Muhajir students. The absence of a significant association suggests that ethnicity does not play a determining role in influencing the outcome among students enrolled in health sciences programs. Economic status also did not show a significant relationship with outcome

levels. Students from the middle economic class constituted the majority of those with good and excellent levels, while students from poor and high economic backgrounds were fewer in number. These findings imply that economic status may not be a major contributing factor to the outcome within this academic setting, possibly due to similar educational resources and learning environments provided by the institution. With regard to academic programs, no statistically significant association was observed between the program of study and outcome levels, students enrolled in BSN (Generic) showed a higher frequency of excellent levels, followed by those in DPT, Pharm-D, and BSPH programs. This pattern may reflect differences in class size or curriculum structure rather than true differences in the outcome, as the overall association remained non-significant. Similarly, academic year did not demonstrate a significant association with outcome levels. However, fourth-year students exhibited a higher proportion of excellent levels compared to students in lower academic years. This trend may be attributed to increased academic exposure, experience, and maturity as students' progress through their programs, although the lack of statistical significance suggests that these differences are not substantial.

CONCLUSION:

This study assessed the association between selected demographic characteristics and outcome levels among undergraduate health sciences students. The findings revealed that the majority of participants demonstrated good to excellent levels, indicating an overall favorable status within the study population. Most demographic variables, including gender, ethnicity, economic status, academic program, academic year, and accommodation, did not show a statistically significant association with outcome levels, suggesting that these factors have minimal influence on the outcome among students. Religion was the only demographic variable found to have a statistically significant association with outcome levels. However, this finding should be interpreted with caution due to the unequal distribution of participants across religious groups.

Overall, the results suggest that the outcome is relatively consistent across diverse demographic backgrounds in the academic setting.

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However, fourth-year students exhibited a higher proportion of excellent levels compared to students in lower academic years

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